

POLITICAL SCIENCES

PEACE-BUILDING: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7828165>

Abstract

In an attempt to lessen violence worldwide, the phenomenon of peace-building has been the subject of numerous empirical investigations. However, researchers are yet to analyze the literature systematically. The present systematic literature review serves two purposes. Firstly, it synthesizes previous research findings to shift the discussion from whether peacekeeping is effective to the more pertinent question of how it can be effective. What factors influence the success or failure of the peace-building process? Secondly, it points to gaps where research can make significant, novel contributions to peace-building. The final objective is to suggest a new research agenda that emphasizes evaluation and informs policymakers about the particular procedures, mission makeups, and mandates that work in peace-building. Co-citation analysis & Bibliographic coupling have been used to organize the extant literature into seven clusters, focusing on peace-building during wars and insurgencies from a multi-dimensional perspective. The domestic, international, and regional factors which either increase or decrease the effectiveness of peacekeeping are also elaborated. The present study could aid in lowering the price of peacekeeping operations, removing specific unfavorable effects of interventions, and saving more lives.

Keywords: Peace-building, process, Conflict, War, Development, Systematic review, Resolutions and Negotiations.

1. INTRODUCTION

There has been a reduction in the number of international wars since the end of World War II because of the establishment of the United Nation's peace-building mechanism and system of collective security. The world's powerful nations realized the importance of preserving peace (Honey, 2009). As a result, Eriksson et al. (2003) concluded that only seven interstate armed conflicts occurred between 1989 and 2003. The Cold War ended in 1989. Of those seven, one was the United States and the coalition fighting the insurgents and agents of al-Qaeda in Iraq and Afghanistan. However, the Russian-Ukrainian war recently shattered the established peace (Matveeva, 2022). The United Nations General Assembly president recently noted that the security council was created in 1945 to ensure that conflicts are resolved peacefully and announced that "The Security Council in its present form is paralyzed and dysfunctional. The Ukraine war is one of the issues that make it quite obvious why the Security Council must be reformed,"¹⁰.

Only a few peace initiatives have succeeded. Only one-third of settlements reached in "identity civil wars"

since 1945 have produced a sustainable, long-lasting peace (Umar et al., 2019). Peace is described by governments, academics, and the general public, as the absence of conflict and physical violence. Various parties to a dispute define peace in different ways. Johan Galtung distinguished between negative and positive peace (Grewal, 2003). Positive peace includes the absence of structural violence (such as poverty-related deaths) and cultural violence (factors that allow people to become numb to injustice or rationalize it).

In contrast, negative peace is the absence of direct violence (such as people being killed). For lasting peace, J. Lewis Rasmussen argues that both positive and negative peace should exist (Lambourne, 2000). The reason for peace not lasting between warring factions is not only due to the opposition to resolution but also often due to the struggle for political power during the implementation of an agreement. There might be issues with the structure and conduct of official negotiations to end (identity) civil wars (Cunningham & Sawyer, 2019).

¹⁰ <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/unsc-paralyzed-and-dysfunctional-says-unga-president-csaba-koros-101675093732618.html>

Existing literature has examined the association between third-party peacekeeping and violence (Dorussen, 2014; Gizelis, Dorussen, and Petrova, 2016; Di Salvatore & Ruggeri, 2017; Sandler, 2017). The research results are unanimous. Almost all researchers conclude that maintaining peace is a very efficient way to stop violence before it starts, lessen it while there is a war, and keep it from happening again after it has finished (Walter et al., 2021). Some studies compared regions and nations that received peacekeeping missions and those that did not. The recipients of peacekeeping missions, all else being equal, suffer less armed conflict, fewer civilian and combatant casualties, fewer mass killings, prolonged post-conflict peace, and fewer subsequent wars. The positive association between peacekeeping and reduced violence is consistent across multiple studies (Beardsley et al., 2019). As a result, there's a movement towards newer formats of peace building such as liberal peace-building. It believes that liberal democracy and a market economy work best to achieve and preserve peace (both domestically and internationally) (Yuan, 2022).

One of the main criticisms of modern peace procedures is that they frequently ignore the causes of the bitterness, particularly the memories and pictures that contribute to it (Baksh, 2022). In the conflict resolution literature, there has been much debate over the years between those who believe that psychosocial/ psychocultural factors have a more prominent role in conflict than structural factors (Ibrahim et al., 2022). The discussion has immediate implications for practice because structuralists emphasize rights, justice, and political issues. In contrast, proponents of the psychocultural viewpoint have placed more emphasis on relationships. They believe in working to dispel ignorance, false beliefs, fears, and hostility between the groups, frequently through cooperative activities and encounters (Bickmore, 2019).

The current article adds to the discussion on the role of peacekeeping in the era of the "pragmatic turn" in international conflict resolution. According to a number of peacekeeping experts, the liberal internationalism problem heralds the potential end of the liberal period of peacebuilding through UN peace operations (de Coning, 2018; Karlsrud, 2019a, 2019b; Wiuff Moe & Stepputat, 2018). They recognized the "pragmatic turn" as a shift away from the lofty goals of UN peace operations as a means of state formation using liberal democratic models, and towards less ambitious plans for "good enough" government and a focus on safeguarding civilians (Hunt, 2019). As additional proof of this change, peacekeeping is seeing hitherto unheard-of pressure from its major financiers to reduce expenses, scale back, and withdraw long-running missions (Holt & Hopkins, 2021). Significant questions are being raised on the efficacy of "peace" interventions by the UN and allies when direct conflicts such as Ukraine and Russia are unresolved (Juma, 2022).

Further, amidst clear evidence that peacekeeping helps stop violence, the United Nations' inability to send peacekeeping forces is detrimental to its credibility (Aubyn, 2022). The extant literature on peacekeeping processes and outcomes is fragmented. Moreover,

the recent Russian-Ukrainian war and the West's role in the war aggravated the need for synthesizing peacebuilding literature. Therefore, the current study investigated the extant literature to extract the factors responsible for the success or failure of the peace-building process. To the author's knowledge, studies have yet to review the peace-building literature systematically.

Thus, the current investigation attempts to synthesize the understanding of the past literature systematically. Maintaining transparency is vital in a literature review. Accordingly, authors need to lay down explicit inclusion criteria for articles. Further, article exclusion should be justified and supported by evidence (Greyson et al., 2019). SLR encourages researchers to examine information on research design, analytical methods, and causal chains (Mohamed et al., 2021).

Additionally, SLR can maintain overall control over the quality of a review by ensuring that evidence is robust and that findings are consistent across the board (Lockwood et al., 2015; Mallet et al., 2012). The rest of the study is structured as follows: The next section, i.e., Section 2 on methodology, deals with the protocols, inclusion-exclusion criteria, and the literature's basic research profile. Section 3 provides descriptive statistics and results. Section 4 includes a discussion and identifies factors leading to the success or failures of the peace-building process, followed by limitations, future research, and a conclusion.

2. METHODOLOGY

A literature study is required to establish an original theoretical model and trace the advancement of a given subject across time. Systematic approaches to literature evaluation can minimize bias and create reliable outcomes (Moher, 2011). Academics have realized the importance of organized reviews while having some papers and problems dedicated only to orderly reviews of scientific literature and other resources (Furunes, 2019). Systematic reviews focused on a particular domain are the most common type. The author used a systematic literature review technique to respond to the research gap in the literature. The study's research questions pertain to the researcher adopting or building their structure (Paul & Benito, 2018). The study used the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) procedure. The procedure included four steps: "identification," "screening," "eligibility," and "inclusion" (Moher, 2009). The "PRISMA method" is frequently utilized for review studies in various fields (Wicaksono & Setiawan, 2022). The following is a detailed description of each step:

2.1 Identification of articles

The authors examined four criteria in selecting articles: keywords, database, time, and article type. The definition of the search phrases was the first step in the investigation. The authors looked through related literature and identified the following keywords "Peacebuilding," "Peacekeeping," "Peace process," and "Peacemaking," which were integrated using Boolean AND, OR. The Scopus database was used to conduct the literature exploration. The cut-off date for identifying publication was January 17, 2023. We checked for terms in the title, keywords, and abstract. The search

yielded 7813 articles initially. Following the initial search, the authors included English articles from 2013 (of the last decade, 2013-23 only) in "peer-reviewed journals." We selected articles published in the areas of Social science, Economics & econometrics, finance,

and decision sciences only. As a result of this procedure, 2464 articles were identified.

The search syntax of the initial query was also attached. The identified articles were further screened and manually analyzed for their subsequent selection.

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TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "peace mak*" OR "peace build*" OR "peace
keep*" OR "peace process*" ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR, 2023 )
OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR, 2022 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR, 2021 )
OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR, 2020 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR, 2019 )
OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR, 2018 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR, 2017 )
OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR, 2016 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR, 2015 )
OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR, 2014 ) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR, 2013 )
) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA, "SOCI" ) OR LIMIT-TO (
SUBJAREA, "ECON" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA, "DECI" ) OR
LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA, "MULT" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE,
"ar" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE, "English" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-
TO ( SRCTYPE, "j" ) )
```

2.1.1 Search syntax

2.2 Articles Screening and refinement

The authors and a set of research scholars read the title, abstracts, and keywords to assess if the paper met the research objectives. We read only journal articles and excluded book reviews or conference papers. The step resulted in the selection of only rigorous and high-quality papers. Accordingly, screening was limited to 2291 articles which were further analyzed. Further, in the subsequent sections, bibliometric analysis and network analysis were performed using Bib Excel and Vos-viewer for in-depth data analysis.

2.3 Analysis and reporting

Two thousand two hundred ninety-one articles were subjected to Bibliometric analysis. Multiple tools, such as HistCite, and Bib-Excel, are available for the bibliometric analysis. The authors used Bib-Excel in this study. It allows greater flexibility and ease in incorporating multiple database files into the software. Also, the data analysis done by the software can be further used as input in other software such as vos-viewer and Gephi (Persson et al., 2009). Bib-Excel requires a dataset in RIS format, which contains all the bibliographic details of the documents to be analyzed (Bankar & Lihitkar, 2019).

After doing the Bibliometric analysis, the authors performed Network analysis to get the dataset clusters. The authors used Vos-viewer to achieve the network diagrams. Both co-citation analysis and bibliographic coupling were performed to obtain the representative articles. Firstly, we performed a co-citation analysis

with a threshold of five (5 interlinkages). It resulted in a total of 244 articles segregated into seven clusters.

Further, bibliographic coupling was performed with a threshold of fifteen (15 interlinkages). It resulted in seven clusters of 240 articles. Accordingly, the authors settled for seven clusters using representative pieces from co-citation and bibliographic analysis.

The researchers further reduced the 240 articles thus obtained. Manually analyzing the content of 240 articles was a tedious task and may compromise the quality of the analysis. Hence, only the top 20 % of the articles belonging to each cluster were further analyzed manually (Shah et al., 2020; Goyal & Kumar, 2021). Accordingly, the authors finally used 52 papers for the content analysis.

3. BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS RESULTS

The study employed bibliometric analysis to examine the available dataset as it is a quantitative method for managing the growing literature in a particular field (Donthu et al., 2021). However, the extant literature also provides that the bibliometric analysis alone cannot replace the conventional literature review methods and can only act as a supplementary method (Feng et al., 2017). Therefore, to make the study robust and generate valuable insights, we further investigated the influential articles in the field using content analysis (e.g., Krippendorff, 2018). Bibliometric analysis used data characteristics such as the year of publication, journal, author, affiliation, keywords, and geography (country).

3.1 Documents by Year

Figure 2: Publication Trend

Figure 2 provides the trendline of the documents published in peace-building in the last decade. Bib-Excel (tag PY) provided the frequency of papers published in a year. Though the field has already been well-de-

finied, there has been exponential growth in publications in the last decade, indicating a rising scholarly interest. A total of 291 articles were published in 2022, and with the onset of 2023, the domain has already received nine publications.

Figure 1: Research framework

Documents by Author

Figure 3: Documents by author

Figure 3 provides the Top 10 most influential authors in the peace-building literature. Many scholars, academicians, and even non-academicians were researching this domain extensively. Using Bib-Excel, we analyzed the frequency of documents published (AU tag in Bib-Excel) by different authors. The frequency was sorted in descending order to get to the domain's Top 10 most influential authors. The criteria for the top 10 authors included both solo or co-authored papers. Oliver P. Richmond and Madhav Joshi were found to be the most influential authors of the domain (See Richmond, (2018) and Joshi & Darby (2013). Fu-

ture researchers can easily use the data for future collaborations and synthesize the extant literature in the field.

3.3 Documents per year by source

Further, we segregated the documents published in this domain and sorted them based on per-year publications in the Top 10 contributing journals. This analysis helps future researchers by providing them with a list of potential study outlets. Peace-building journal published the most articles in 2022; Peace and Conflict published the most in 2021; Third World Quarterly published the most in 2020.

Figure 4: Publication trend in the Top 10 journals

The journals with more publications indicate more significant interest in these journals for publishing articles relevant to the domain.

3.4 Documents by Affiliation

Figure 5 provides the most influential institutes publishing in peace-building. Bib-Excel was used to get the list of institutes affiliated with the publishing authors and sorted in descending order. Such analysis

helps the scholars know about the institutes supporting research in the domain and can guide future collaborations and studies. The analysis provides that Queen's University Belfast has supported the publication of the most articles in the field, followed by Ulster university and the university of Manchester.

Figure 5: Top 10 affiliating institutes

3.5 Documents by Country

Every geographic region or country is concerned about its economic growth, research, and development. Peace is a necessary condition for the same (Coulomb & Bellais, 2008). Figure 6 shows that the United Kingdom has published the most articles, with a total of 500+ articles, followed by the United States having 466

articles, Australia having 136 articles, and Germany having 110 articles. The list indicates the dominance of developed countries in publishing articles relevant to this domain. Hence, it provides an immense opportunity for authors from developing nations to contribute more towards this domain and their country's economic growth.

Figure 6: Top 10 contributing nations

3.6 Top contributing journals

As per the preliminary analysis done using Bib-Excel, more than 186 journals have contributed to this domain, publishing around 2291 articles in the last decade from 2013 to 2023. However, figure 6 provides the top 10 contributing journals in peace-building. A total of 372 papers have been published in the top 10 journals,

i.e., 16.24 % of the total publications belong to these journals. Third World Quarterly has published the most articles, i.e., 77 articles, followed by Peace and Conflict, having 75 pieces, and conflict, security & development, 69 articles. Researchers can target these journals to have greater chances of manuscript acceptance.

Figure 7: Top contributing journals

3.7 Frequently used keywords

Keyword statistics have been a widely cherished dataset analysis tool for ages. Statistics is a scientific method for detecting relationships between the sub-fields of a particular domain (He, 1999). Bib-Excel has been used to conduct this analysis. The authors did a comparative analysis of the main keywords having a high frequency in the documents related to peace-building. Figure 8 lists the top 20 keywords widely used in

articles. Researchers have used the "Peace process" the most, i.e., 976 times, followed by "peacekeeping" 276 times and peace-building 190 times. The analysis further indicates the usage of keywords like "war," "human rights," "women's status," and "religion." It meant articles published in this domain focused on women, religion, and wars in different regions.

Figure 8 Frequently used keywords

4. NETWORK ANALYSIS

Network analysis tools may evaluate and offer detailed information about the links between the articles, citations, and co-citations. The analysis can aid in finding relevant research trends (Zupic & Cater, 2015). Different tools, such as Pajek, Vos-viewer, Hist-Cite, and Gephi, are available. Hist-Cite is confined to Web of

Science data, whereas Pajek works with the ".net" file format only (Sarkar et al., 2022). However, vos-viewer has no such constraints and provides for adjustments in network visualization. Hence, vos-viewer was used for the study.

Each article contains distinct information fields for conducting the analysis, and data is collected from each

Figure 10. Citation analysis network visualization

4.3 Clustering: classifying the extant literature

The nodes in a network can be classified into clusters or themes, where the density of edges is larger between nodes within the same cluster compared to the edges between the nodes of different clusters (Claust et al., 2004; Leydesdorff, 2011). Although, nodes represent articles in a research field that has limited connections to papers in other clusters or study areas. Data clustering using vos-viewer may be used as a classification method to group a set of provided articles (Radicchi et al., 2004). It enables the typological study of networks by identifying subjects, inter-relationships, and cooperation patterns.

Three factors lead to the adoption of network analysis. First off, network analysis gives consumers the chance to illustrate a dynamic knowledge area based on connections and advancements in science. Second, it is a quantitative approach that mathematically and statistically charts the link between publications (Si et al., 2019). It has been extensively utilized by researchers to choose relevant papers for content

analysis (Merigo & Yang, 2017; Wang et al., 2017; Xu et al., 2020). The hybrid analysis using co-citation and bibliographic coupling yielded seven clusters (Table 2).

From a scientific standpoint, the citation linkages between publications are systematically mapped using co-citation (Marshakova, 1973; Small, 1973) and bibliographic coupling (Kessler, 1963) analysis. If papers cite or are cited by each other more frequently, the likelihood that they represent the same clusters and approaches increases (Hjrlund, 2013). Since it takes a long time to properly show the entire citation picture using a less accurate time link, we do not employ direct citation analysis to identify representative papers. A threshold level of five interlinkages has been used for extracting the representative articles using the co-citation and the bibliographic coupling analysis. Table 2 summarizes the articles of each cluster.

Further, Figure 11 & 12 presents the network visualization of the co-citation analysis and bibliographic coupling.

Table 2

Clustering Analysis (representative articles)	
CLUSTERS	No. of Articles
Cluster 1	68
Cluster 2	52
Cluster 3	38
Cluster 4	26
Cluster 5	21
Cluster 6	19
Cluster 7	16

Table 3

Articles used in content analysis

CLUSTERS	No. of Articles
Cluster 1	12
Cluster 2	9
Cluster 3	8
Cluster 4	7
Cluster 5	6
Cluster 6	5
Cluster 7	5

Cluster 1: Peace-building

This cluster focuses on the positive aspect of peace-building and talks about various theoretical concepts underlying peace-building. Some notable authors, such as Vasilopoulos (2018), emphasized the idea of positive peace. He strongly advocated that peace-building opportunities not only lie during the war but exist everywhere. He made a distinction between positive and negative peace in this way. Negative peace "is the absence of violence or war," and positive peace "is the integration of human society" (Galtung, 1964, p. 2). According to South (2018), outside players that want to "think and work politically" should go beyond conventional peace-building and development initiatives based on bolstering the state. They ought to use conflict-aware and context-sensitive strategies.

Moreover, the extant literature on peace-building considered it a bureaucratic process (Richmond, 2018). Hence, the field requires anthropological and ethnographic sensitivity. Parties should address trust, security, and economic dependence at the initial level to prevent the failure of the peace-building process (Mason, 2013). Further, the success of peace-building relies on engagement with civil society and the degree of international involvement (South & Joll, 2016). Most importantly, locals' participation in peace-building plays a significant role (Leonardsson & Rudd, 2015; Kappler, 2015; Randazzo, 2016). The parties to peace-building hold different assumptions, leading to the process's failure (Autesserre, 2017). Moreover, the literature on inclusion of locals is rising, however, there is debate around whom to treat as locals (Philipsen, 2022). Papers have also paid attention to third-party involvement for better peace-building negotiations (Beardsley et al., 2019). However, despite all the factors, international institutions like the UN have a vital role (Doyle et al., 2006), as stabilizing peace is more complex than achieving a mere consensus (Hartzell et al., 2001).

Cluster 2: Impact on Society & Geopolitics

Researchers need to pay more attention to the impact of wars and insurgencies on society and the political situation of a region (Reuveni & Madigan, 2019; Ide, 2020). Cluster 2 contains articles that address the same. These disputes cause tension and are expensive both financially and emotionally (Bar-Tal, 1998). Wars frequently start due to extreme inequality, lack of political rights, or societal, racial, and religious divisions (Gethin et al., 2021; Collier & Hoeffler, 2004). Accordingly, they have a significant negative influence on society. Many studies have shown how tourism fosters societal peace (Litvin, 2020). For instance, some authors argue that if tourism is to contribute to peace, it

must address the more significant structural factors determining the strength of civil society, particularly the operation of reciprocity (Scott, 2012). After September 11, 2001, scholarship in and outside political geography has critically engaged with issues of conflict, security, and terror (Schenk et al., 2022; Dodds & Ingram, 2009; Gregory, 2010; Pain and Smith, 2008). War dominates the literature on peace and war, with glances at peace having abstract macro-level or isolated empirical occurrences (Mac Ginty, 2021; Williams & McConnell, 2011). Wars bring shift in social values & contribute towards societal transformation. Hence, peace-building should be a part of everyday practice in the society (Khedir, 2022).

Cluster 3: Hybrid forms of peace

Apart from the previously discussed literature, peace literature also finds its roots in political psychology and other uncommon domains. Peaceful conflict resolution is hampered by the ethos of conflict, collective memory, collective emotional orientation, and its components (Bar-tal, 2019). These obstacles, which have their roots in the culture of conflict, inhibit individuals from digesting information in a way that leads to fresh viewpoints. Literature defines barriers as "an integrated operation of cognitive, emotional and motivational processes, combined with a pre-existing repertoire of rigid conflict supporting beliefs, world views and emotions that result in selective, biased and distorting information processing" (Tallodi & Tallodi, 2019; Bar-Tal & Halperin, 2011, p. 220).

Hybrid peace is made possible by the intersection of locally based peace initiatives with international backing and indigenous, traditional, and customary customs. Hybrid peace is the result of the interaction of local actors' capacities to offer and uphold alternate forms of peacemaking, as well as their capacities to reject, ignore, or adapt liberal peace approaches (Paalo & Issifu, 2021; Ginty, 2010). Technology is going to play a bigger role in the peace-building processes (Romanelli, 2021; Alcazar, 2006). It can offer help in maintaining dialogues & co-operation. Also, emerging medias such as social-media, technology based news platforms will have a wider impact (Adeshina, 2022). For peace to last, local actors must be able to resist, defy, or adapt to liberal peace initiatives, and liberal peace agents, networks, and structures must be able to incentivize compliance (Ginty, 2010).

Cluster 4: Politics behind war & gender

To a greater extent, the politics that goes on before & after war plays a more significant role in sustaining peace. However, researchers still need to pay attention

to these contexts (De Coning, 2016). Since the conclusion of the Cold War, there have been more international peace interventions, with UN operations, non-governmental organizations, funders, diplomatic missions, and regional organizations becoming more prevalent and powerful (Dorussen, 2022; Autesserre, 2011; Paris & Sisk, 2009). For academics, professionals, and citizens of post-war governments, figuring out what influences these projects' performance is crucial (Autesserre, 2014). A peace-building project, program, or intervention is successful when most of those involved believe it has promoted peace in the intervention area (Newman, 2011). The involved parties include both the project's implementers (international interveners and local peace-builders) and intended beneficiaries (local elite and ordinary citizens) (Billon, 2001). Armed conflict in the post-Cold War era is becoming more and more distinct by a particular political ecology connected to the geography and political economy of natural resources (Ide et al., 2022; Westing, 1986). The UN has worked to secure women's involvement in peace. It particularly concerns women's participation in fostering peace and post-conflict rehabilitation. It is the Security Council's most current statement on the subject of "women and peace and security." (Shepherd, 2011).

Cluster 5: Strategies behind peace-building

This cluster consists of articles building upon the strategies that help in better and sustained peace-building. Because of its strong emphasis on universal standards and generic solutions, both in theory and in reality, the consensus has been criticized for its liberal and apolitical approach, which frequently omits political components (Aggestam et al., 2015). Inclusion is one of the strategies that literature has emphasized. The concept of "inclusion" has become vital in promoting peace. However, its precise meaning is unclear, as are presumptions on the connection between inclusiveness and peace (Hirblinger & Landau, 2020). Literature establishes three different inclusion objectives. Building a more legitimate peace is the first one. Empowering and defending certain actor groups is the second. And finally, changing the socio-political mechanisms that fuel conflict is the third (Wallenstein et al., 2014). Also, some strategies build upon mediation and negotiation during armed conflicts (Lederach, 2005). Further, the extant literature provides eight practices that help in inculcating a habit of everyday peace. They are avoidance, watching/reading, ambiguity, shielding, civility, reciprocity, solidarity and compromise (Ware et al., 2022).

Cluster 6: Resisting wars and settlements

This cluster provides for the aftermath of war and further explains how parties may resist wars and achieve settlements (Pechenkina & Thomas, 2020; Toft, 2010; Walter, 2002). Contrary to predictions, the empirical research findings in the literature imply that forced recruitment increases postwar political engagement. Former abductees have a 27% higher likelihood of voting and a doubled possibility of serving as community leaders (Gallegos, 2021; Blattman, 2009). Former combatants' disarmament, demobilization, reinsertion,

and reintegration (DDRR) process crucially impact the transition from conflict to peace. The success or failure of the DDRR process strongly affects any society's post-conflict long-term stability (Ansorg & Gordon, 2019; Knight & Ozerdem, 2004). Also, the literature has suggested ways for communities to protect themselves and restore peace (Kaplan, 2017). However, it still requires further empirical validation.

Cluster 7: Psychology of war & human security

This cluster provides insights into psychological factors that promote war. It also sheds light on some that help to prevent it. Over the past two decades, the field of evolutionary warfare has grown significantly (Lopez, 2017). Instead of adaptationist interpretations of the psychology at its core, it has a tendency to concentrate on the ancestors, prevalence, and weapons of battle. The norms in international politics determine whether, how much, which, and whose ideas matter (Acharya, 2014). The constructivist theorists focus on situations when "good" global norms triumph over "bad" local beliefs and practices (Acharya, 2004). Drawing on the strength of shared experience, women have realized that the political demands of millions shout louder than the cries of a few lonely voices (Crenshaw, 2014). Media news significantly impacts the psychology of war (Linden & Roozenbeek, 2020; Wolfsfeld, 2004). When combined with human security, the information takes different shapes and turns (Paris, 2001). Further, the local politicians' religious ethos, culture, and ideology often shape the psychology behind the war (Williams, 1996). Thus, peace-building is a multi-dimensional phenomenon explored in different domains such as psychology, sociology, or history.

6. Implications

The current study synthesizes the extant literature on peace-building and provides future research agendas. The literature has been segmented into seven clusters and provides vibrant details about each cluster. The study has implications for various peace-building stakeholders, be it the nations under war, locals, international organizations, or the government. First of all, the study helps academicians by summarizing and collating the entire literature on peace-building and helping them find new areas that need further investigation. Second, the study provides that war and peace-building are not uni-dimensional, and they get affected by multiple factors, such as psychological and contextual. Third, the study reviews both positive and negative forms of peace. It further sheds light on hybrid forms of peace-building and provides for future research agendas.

7. Limitations and Future research directions

After synthesizing the extant literature, the current study provides the future research direction for scholars to investigate less explored areas. Even though the study has many contributions, it has a few limitations. First, keyword choice for search queries can only be partially exhaustive. Therefore, future scholars can synthesize the literature by using more keywords. Second, the authors conducted the content analysis using each cluster's top papers. Future researchers can take larger datasets for a better understanding of the literature. Moreover, the review was restricted to the literature

pertaining to the last decade, more comprehensive study could be undertaken by the future scholars.

Further, most of the existing studies find its roots in developed nations such as USA, UK, Germany & Australia. Thus, providing immense opportunities to the third world nations especially the Asian, African & Latin American nations to publish in the domain. Also, literature has examined various forms of peace and is already into hybrid peace (Ginty, 2010). However, the impact of rising technology usage on the peace-building process needs further exploration. Moreover, there has been lack of studies drawing from multiple-nations. Hence, scholars can explore how peace-building and sustaining differs across developed and developing nations? and can there be a “technological turn” similar to the “local turn” evident in the literature (Cheshmehzangi, 2022; Barrera et al., 2022).

8. Conclusion

Peace-building has been the focus of various studies to reduce bloodshed globally. The systematic study of peace-building as a concept, however, is lacking. The article conducts a systematic review of the body of research on peace-building. It organizes it into seven clusters, focusing on the psychological effects of wars and insurgencies as well as the effects of wars and insurgencies on society and hybrid forms of peace. Additionally, it offers essential bibliometric analysis descriptions, including the publication year, journal, author, affiliation, keywords, and geographic location. The study concludes by proposing a new research agenda that prioritizes evaluation and provides policymakers with information on the specific processes, mission compositions, and mandates that are effective in peace-building.

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